

Potassium Bromate as an Oxidising Agent. A Kinetic Study of Diols in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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Michaelis Menten kinetics have been observed for the oxidation of diols by bromate ion in sulphuric and perchloric acid solution of 1 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength. The reaction has a first order dependence on Br(V) concentration. The effect of ionic strength is marginal, but the reaction rate is accelerated with acidity, and the rate constant follows the H₀ function. Reactions in acetic acid-water mixtures indicate that the dielectric constant has an influence on the reaction kinetics. It is observed that increase in acetic acid content of the medium increases the rate, and a linear relationship is observed when log k₁ is plotted against 1/D and against D - 1/2D + 1. To account the observed rate law, the proposed mechanism assumes an intermediate being formed from the protonated oxidant (HBrO₃, K₁ = 0.51 l mol⁻¹; and H₂BrO₃⁺, K₂ = 0.20 l²mol⁻²) and a molecule of diol, which decomposes (both in the normal way as well as in cleavage) to yield identifiable products. The observed thermodynamic parameters are also discussed.

THOUGH several oxidants have been employed for the oxidation of glycols, the mechanism of glycol fission has been the subject of much controversial discussion in which the relative merits of homolytic bond fission and heterolytic decomposition of the intermediate cyclic complexes have been argued¹⁻⁵. However, so many reagents can effect selective 1 : 2 glycol fission, that the exact mechanism of the reaction may not be independent of the chemical nature of the oxidiser.

In connection with the homolytic mechanism for this reaction, the oxidation of 1 : 2 glycols by the acid bromate, to which we have already directed attention⁶ is of particular interest. We have, therefore, studied kinetically the oxidation of diols (ethanediol, butane-1,2-; -1,3-; -1,4- and -2,3-diols) by bromate ion in the presence of acid, which has not been investigated so far. Hence, the present investigation was undertaken to fill the lacunae good.

Experimental

Ethanediol (AnalaR, B.D.H.), butane-1,2-; -1,3-; -1,4- and -2,3-diol (Fluka) were used, and distilled under vacuum before use. Acetic acid (AnalaR, B.D.H.) was purified by fractional distillation after refluxing with chromium trioxide and acetic anhydride. Only the fractions of distillate, boiling at 118° was collected and used as such for kinetic studies. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and were purified either by distillation or by recrystallisation.

Solutions of diol and bromate were thermostated in requisite proportions in separate flasks for about

1.5 h before mixing. The progress of the reaction was followed iodometrically to a starch end point. The pseudo first-order rate constants (k₁) were calculated from the plot of log[BrO₃⁻]_t against time, and second order rate constants (k₂) were obtained by dividing k₁ with [diol]. All the values of rate constant were the average of two or more experiments, the accuracy being ± 3% or better. Solvents were stable under the experimental conditions. The oxidation products were identified with their characteristic spot tests, and the product bromide ion was identified with AgNO₃ test.

Results

It is worth to mention that the production of bromine (due to the interaction of Br(V) and Br⁻ ions) and its subsequent oxidation was eliminated by the initial addition of mercuric acetate, which complexes Br⁻ (product) as unionised HgBr₂ or HgBr₂⁺, without involving in the kinetic studies.

All the reactions have been carried out under the experimental conditions where the concentration of substrate is ten times greater than that of Br(V). The first order dependence on the [bromate] was indicated not only by the linearity of the first order plots, but also by the observed independence of the first order rate constants (k₁) on different initial Br(V) concentration, varied from 2.0 to 20.0 × 10⁻⁴ l mol⁻¹ in a number of steps at constant concentrations of other reagents (Table 1).

It has been observed that k_{obs} increases with the increase in substrate concentration (Table 2), and the slopes obtained from the plots of log k_{obs} against log[diol] were 0.94, 0.93, 0.96, 0.88 and 0.85 for ethanediol, butane-1,2-diol, butane-1,3-diol, butane-1,4-

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [BROMATE] ON k_1 IN BROMATE-DIOL SYSTEM AT $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$
 [diol]=0.01 M, $[H_2SO_4]=1.0$ M, $[Hg(OAc)_2]=0.002$ M, AcOH : $H_2O=30 : 70$ (v/v)

[BrO ₃] × 10 ⁴ M	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1**}$									
	Ethane-1,2-diol		Butane-1,2-diol		Butane-1,3-diol		Butane-1,4-diol		Butane-2,3-diol	
2.00	3.95 (1.09)	*8.73 (2.85)	3.22 (0.94)	*6.34 (1.87)	3.55 (0.82)	*7.67 (2.17)	4.71 (1.49)	*10.01 (3.55)	2.96 (0.89)	*5.77 (1.70)
4.00	3.94 (1.07)	8.71 (2.88)	3.27 (0.92)	6.30 (1.82)	3.59 (0.88)	7.61 (2.11)	5.02 (1.40)	9.81 (3.50)	3.04 (0.88)	5.72 (1.71)
8.00	3.92 (1.00)	8.74 (2.82)	3.21 (0.94)	6.33 (1.84)	3.55 (0.83)	7.70 (2.16)	4.92 (1.42)	10.02 (3.47)	3.07 (0.86)	5.75 (1.74)
10.00	3.94 (1.08)	8.73 (2.84)	3.20 (0.97)	6.31 (1.80)	3.54 (0.85)	7.67 (2.22)	4.89 (1.49)	10.07 (3.51)	3.01 (0.87)	5.76 (1.76)
12.00	3.93 (1.09)	8.70 (2.86)	3.28 (0.93)	6.37 (1.83)	3.54 (0.87)	7.68 (2.17)	5.00 (1.47)	10.00 (3.49)	2.99 (0.87)	5.68 (1.82)
16.00	3.90 (1.10)	8.64 (2.83)	3.26 (0.92)	6.38 (1.85)	3.51 (0.86)	7.63 (2.14)	4.89 (1.41)	9.99 (3.50)	3.02 (0.84)	5.80 (1.81)
20.00	3.96 (1.07)	8.64 (2.85)	3.21 (0.94)	6.31 (1.80)	3.55 (0.89)	7.69 (2.18)	4.90 (1.46)	9.86 (3.42)	2.99 (0.90)	5.70 (1.72)

 * At 50° .

** Paranthesis values obtained in acid perchloric (1.0 M) media.

diol, and butane-2,3-diol, respectively. The dependence of the k_{obs} values on the [substrate] are also consistent with the Michaelis Menten's kinetics in each case.

 TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING [SUBSTRATE] ON REACTION RATE AT $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$

[BrO₃]=0.001 M, $[H_2SO_4]=1.00$ M, $[Hg(OAc)_2]=0.002$ M, HOAc : $H_2O=30 : 70$ (v/v)

[diol] × 10 ³ M	$k_{obs} \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1**}$				
	Ethane-1,2-diol	Butane-1,2-diol	Butane-1,3-diol	Butane-1,4-diol	Butane-2,3-diol
0.50	2.12 (0.71)	1.74	1.20	2.47	1.59
0.75	3.08 (0.98)	2.51	2.74	3.68	2.40
1.00	3.94 (1.23)	3.20	3.54	4.89	3.01
1.50	6.00 (1.74)	4.73	5.18	6.90	4.61
2.00	7.85 (2.30)	6.31	7.29	8.44	5.85
4.00	16.31 (5.02)	11.66	14.00	16.01	10.74
6.00	22.07 (7.06)	16.62	20.01	23.03	14.20
10.00	37.24 (11.10)	30.33	33.98	42.12	26.52

* Paranthesis values obtained in perchloric acid (1.0 M) media.

To isolate the effect of $[H^+]$, experiments were set up under the conditions $[H^+]_0 \gg [diol]_0 \gg [Br(V)]$. It is noticed that increase in [acid] brought an increase in the reaction rate and the observed rate constants at different $[H_2SO_4]$ and $[HClO_4]$ are shown in Table 3. A change in the ionic strength, studied by varying $NaHSO_4$ and $NaClO_4$, has marginal effect, hence the acceleration caused by $HClO_4$ and H_2SO_4 is only due to the H^+ catalysis. The plot of k_1 vs [acid] yields a curve. The other plot, $\log k_1$ vs $\log [acid]_0$ is also a curve, whose slope

changes with increasing concentration of acid. But the plot of $\log k_1$ against H_0 rather than H_R is linear with slopes ranging from 1.2 to 1.5. The nonparticipation of water molecule in the rate limiting step was also supported from the value of slopes (Table 3) obtained in Bunnett's plot.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING [ACID] ON RATE OF REACTION

[Oxidant]=0.001 M, [Substrate]=0.01 M, Temp.= $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Mercuric acetate=0.002 M; $H_2O : HOAc=70 : 30$ (v/v)

[H ⁺] M	$k, \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$				
	Ethane-1,2-diol	Butane-1,2-diol	Butane-1,3-diol	Butane-1,4-diol	Butane-2,3-diol
Sulphuric acid					
0.50	1.06	0.91	0.90	1.28	0.96
0.75	2.08	1.84	2.00	2.40	1.73
1.00	3.94	3.20	3.54	4.89	3.01
1.25	6.40	5.48	6.71	7.68	5.02
1.50	10.97	7.88	9.84	14.03	7.09
2.00	25.52	22.42	25.75	35.90	16.50
n*	1.40	1.32	1.50	1.44	1.26
w*	-10.50	-5.80	-11.43	-14.11	-6.80
Perchloric acid					
0.50	0.44	0.40	0.35	0.57	0.39
1.00	1.09	0.94	0.85	1.49	0.88
1.50	2.55	2.00	1.92	3.85	1.84
1.75	3.84	2.84	—	4.79	—
2.00	6.48	3.88	3.90	7.88	3.40
2.50	—	9.01	8.60	—	6.20
n*	1.46	1.26	1.25	1.27	1.28
w*	-10.66	-4.71	-5.00	-6.25	-1.20

* Slopes obtained from Hammett (n) and Bunnett (w) plots.

An investigation of reaction rates at different proportions of acetic acid and water shows that, increase in the percentage of acetic acid enhances the reaction rate (Table 4). Further, a plot of $\log k_2$ vs $1/D$ and vs $D - 1/2D + 1$ is linear.

For determining the activation parameters the reaction was studied at different temperatures (298

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF THE MEDIUM^a

HOAc-H ₂ O ^b	k ₁ × 10 ³ l mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹				
v/v	Ethane diol	Butane 2,3-diol	Butane 1,2-diol	Butane 1,3-diol	Butane 1,4-diol
10-90 (66.67)	1.77	1.21	1.30	1.34	1.79
20-80 (59.88)	2.88	1.77	1.82	2.30	2.88
30-70 (53.18)	3.94	3.01	3.22	3.55	4.90
40-60 (46.48)	7.68	5.76	6.01	6.24	8.68
50-50 (39.76)	18.32	13.43	15.16	15.96	21.51
60-40 (33.13)	50.86	36.83	40.98	42.78	56.48

^a Other conditions as in Tables 1 and 2.
^b Paranthesis values, dielectric constant of the media calculated by an approximate validity method at 40°.

to 333 K) and the data were found to follow Arrhenius equation. The energy of activation (E_a) and its related thermodynamic parameters were evaluated and are incorporated in Table 5.

The reaction shows no indication of being free radical in nature, since it failed to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile or acrylamide under nitrogen.

Discussion

The reaction between diol and bromate has been shown to be bimolecular. The reaction is probably not one between two oppositely charged ions in which case there should have been considerable ionic strength effect, and also large variation in rate when solvent polarity is changed. According to Amis model a positive slope in the plot of log k₂ vs 1/D points out to be the reaction between a cation and dipole. For the same reaction, log k₂ vs D-1/2D+1 is also linear with negative slope, indicating the reaction between two dipoles according to Kirkwood.

Increase in rate with increasing [H⁺] indicates the involvement of a proton in the rate equation. But the influence of [acid] on the rate of reaction cannot be traced to the substrate, because the protonation of bromate ions is more probable than that of diol. Hence, the reactive species is the protonated bromate ions.

According to Barton and Wright⁷, and Anbar and Guttmann⁸ the following equilibrium is associated with an acid solution of halate ions.

In the present study the following equilibrium can be invoked to explain the acid dependence and the effect of dielectric constant.

It is highly probable that both HBrO₃ and H₂BrO₃⁺ (K₁=0.51 l mol⁻¹ and K₂=0.20 l² mol⁻²)⁹ are the active species resulting in a mixed order in [H⁺] (slopes obtained from the plots of log k₁ vs H₀ are 1.2 to 1.5).

The fact that the order in diol (<1) is consistent with the assumption that equilibrium involving in complex formation between acid bromate and diol preceded the rate limiting step. The formation of acid bromatediol ester prior to the rate limiting step is also indicated by the Michaelis Menten plot (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Representative Michaelis Menten plots of diols at 40 ± 0.01°. (A) Butane-1,4-diol, (B) Ethanediol, (C) Butane-1,3-diol, (D) Butane-1,2-diol, (E) Butane-2,3-diol, (F) Ethanediol (in HClO₄ media).

Consistent with the above features of the reaction the following scheme can be proposed.

An interesting conclusion regarding the mechanism can be drawn; by the study of products

obtained. The oxidation products of diol were glyoxal and formaldehyde, which were identified by their characteristic spot tests with phenylhydrazine¹⁰ and chromotropic acid¹⁰, respectively. Acetaldehyde and 2,3-diketo compounds resulted when butane-2,3-diol was used, and identified by their characteristic tests with 2,4-DNP and nickel(II) hydroxylamine hydrochloride¹⁰ and also with indole¹⁰, respectively. Only the aldehydic products have been identified if butane-1,4-diol is used.

This suggests that the oxidation to carbonyl compounds is taking place simultaneously both in the normal way and also by cleavage. Hence, it can be concluded that when H of C-H bond is attacked the normal way of oxidation to carbonyl products takes place. But, when H of O-H is attacked then the rupture of C-C bond occurs with the formation of cleavage products.

Accordingly, the rate determining step of the reaction could be considered to be the disproportionation of the intermediate ester complex [C] involving a C-H and (or) C-C fission in the rate limiting step. The possible C-H and C-C fission is also supported by the final oxidation products.

The breakdown of [C₁] may be visualised as

and

The total Br(V) concentration is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{Br(V)}]_{\text{T}} &= [\text{BrO}_3^-] + [\text{HBrO}_3] + [\text{H}_2\text{BrO}_3^+] + [\text{C}_1] + [\text{C}_2] \\ &= [\text{H}_2\text{BrO}_3^+] \left\{ \frac{1}{K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{1}{K_1 [\text{H}^+]} + 1 + \frac{K_3 [\text{diol}]}{K_2 [\text{H}^+]} + K_4 [\text{diol}] \right\} \\ &= [\text{H}_2\text{BrO}_3^+] \left\{ \frac{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 K_3 [\text{diol}] [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 K_4 [\text{diol}] [\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{H}_2\text{BrO}_3^+] = \frac{K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{Br(V)}]_{\text{T}}}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 K_3 [\text{diol}] [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 K_4 [\text{diol}] [\text{H}^+]^2}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{Br(V)}]_{\text{T}} &= [\text{HBrO}_3] \left\{ \frac{1}{K_1 [\text{H}^+]} + 1 + K_2 [\text{H}^+] + K_3 [\text{diol}] + K_2 K_4 [\text{diol}] [\text{H}^+] \right\} \\ &= [\text{HBrO}_3] \left\{ \frac{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 K_3 [\text{diol}] [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 K_4 [\text{diol}] [\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1 [\text{H}^+]} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

It seems that the primary reaction is essentially a C-H bond fission under these reaction conditions, leading to hydroxy aldehydes or hydroxy ketones (butane-2,3-diol) in the first instance. The primary oxidation product with butane-1,4-diol by vanadium¹¹ and chromic acid¹² have also been identified as the hydroxy aldehyde.

Similarly the breakdown of complex [C₂] is as

and

At the end of the reaction all products were present in the reaction mixture at low bromate concentration, but at higher oxidant concentration only acid products have been observed. The intermediates Br(III) and Br(I) are involved in fast steps leading to bromide ion as the final product, which has been detected with silver nitrate.

It is seen from the kinetic data (Table 5) that, butane-1,4-diol reacts faster than ethanediol. Similarly, comparing secondary glycols, butane-1,3-diol reacts faster than butane-1,2-diols. This seems to point out that, compounds having *vic*-hydroxyl react the slowest, indicating that there is no cyclic mechanism operating.

The rate law for the above mechanism obtained is as follows.

Therefore,

$$[\text{HBrO}_3] = \frac{K_1[\text{H}^+][\text{Br(V)}]_T}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1K_3[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2K_4[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+]^2}$$

thus, $[\text{C}_1] = K_3[\text{diol}][\text{HBrO}_3]$

$$= \frac{K_1K_3[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+][\text{Br(V)}]_T}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1K_3[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2K_4[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+]^2}$$

and $[\text{C}_2] = K_4[\text{diol}][\text{H}_2\text{BrO}_3^+]$

$$= \frac{K_1K_4[\text{H}^+]^2[\text{Br(V)}]_T}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1K_3[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2K_4[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+]^2}$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{C}_1]}{dt} = k_a[\text{C}_1] \quad \text{and} \quad -\frac{d[\text{C}_2]}{dt} = k_b[\text{C}_2]$$

Hence, the total rate fall of $[\text{Br(V)}]_T$ is given by

$$v = \left\{ -\frac{d[\text{C}_1]}{dt} \right\} + \left\{ -\frac{d[\text{C}_2]}{dt} \right\} = -\frac{d[\text{Br(V)}]_T}{dt}$$

$$= \frac{\{k_aK_1K_3[\text{H}^+] + k_bK_1K_2K_4[\text{H}^+]^2\} [\text{diol}] [\text{Br(V)}]_T}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1K_3[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2K_4[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+]^2}$$

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS* IN ACID BROMATE OXIDATION OF DIOLS AT 40°

[Substrate] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, [Oxidant] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]/[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0$ M,
[Mercuric acetate] = 2.0×10^{-3} M, Dielectric constant = 53.18

Substrate	$k_2 \times 10^3$ 1 mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	PZ 1 mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Acid sulphuric						
Ethanediol	3.96 (0.76)	61.89 (63.98)	85.19 (89.49)	59.29 (61.33)	82.73 (89.91)	8.5×10^9 (3.6×10^9)
Butane-1,2-diol	3.22 (0.62)	60.13 (68.74)	85.70 (89.99)	57.53 (66.18)	90.05 (76.22)	1.3×10^9 (6.8×10^9)
Butane-1,3-diol	3.54 (0.86)	64.20 (69.73)	85.57 (89.18)	61.60 (67.13)	76.36 (70.43)	6.7×10^9 (1.4×10^9)
Butane-1,4-diol	4.89 (0.96)	63.80 (89.33)	88.80 (88.91)	61.20 (86.72)	88.13 (6.97)	1.6×10^9 (2.8×10^{13})
Butane-2,3-diol	3.01 (0.48)	56.63 (68.36)	85.93 (90.71)	54.02 (65.76)	101.88 (79.70)	3.1×10^7 (4.5×10^9)
Acid perchloric						
Ethanediol	1.17 (0.16)	70.82 (73.37)	83.40 (93.57)	68.22 (70.77)	64.44 (72.81)	2.8×10^9 (2.8×10^9)
Butane-1,2-diol	0.94 (0.11)	65.17 (76.18)	86.65 (94.75)	62.57 (73.57)	76.95 (59.33)	2.9×10^9 (5.1×10^9)
Butane-1,3-diol	0.85 (0.13)	71.78 (83.74)	89.21 (94.12)	69.19 (81.14)	63.98 (41.43)	2.9×10^9 (4.5×10^{10})
Butane-1,4-diol	1.49 (0.22)	71.77 (95.71)	87.76 (93.52)	69.18 (93.10)	59.33 (1.33)	5.6×10^9 (5.6×10^{12})
Butane-2,3-diol	0.88 (0.09)	59.82 (74.53)	89.14 (94.95)	57.21 (71.92)	101.80 (73.54)	3.0×10^7 (9.3×10^9)

* Parenthesis values obtained in aqueous media (D = 73.28)

The above equation explains the variable order in acid concentration and also Michaelis Menten kinetic behaviour of substrate. The mechanism is further corroborated by the solvent influence on the reaction. The intermediate ester(s) is less polar than the reactants due to dispersal of charge, hence decreasing polarity of the solvent would be expected to stabilise the bromate ester in preference to the reactants, thereby enhancing the rate. Such a solvent influence has actually been observed; the rate constant increases with increasing percentage of acetic acid in the medium (Table 4).

Thermodynamic parameters for all diols studied may be explained on the basis of the isokinetic relationship^{1,2}. For a series of compounds of slightly different structure but undergoing a reaction essentially of the same mechanism, that $\Delta G^\ddagger$ values may be more or less constant with the relative changes in enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H^\ddagger$) and the entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger$). A linear relationship between the entropy and enthalpy of activation has been found in accordance with the equation, $\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$, where β is the isokinetic temperature. The plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ in the present case have been found to

be linear ($r=0.998$, $s=0.04$) with a slope, $\beta=273$ (271)* and 275 (274)* in H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ (Figs. 2A, B and 2C, D) medium, respectively, suggesting the applicability of isokinetic relationship.

Fig. 2. Plot of enthalpy of activation vs entropy of activation [A-D] and Exner plots [E-H]. (A, E) Acid sulphuric and aqueous acetic acid media, (B, F) Acid sulphuric in aqueous media, (C, G) Acid perchloric and aqueous acetic acid media, (D, H) Acid perchloric in aqueous media.

Notwithstanding this result, we have resorted β from Exner's plot. Better values of β can be obtained from a log-log plot of the rate constant at two different temperatures as advocated by Exner¹⁴. The value of β evaluated in this manner from the plot of $\log k_{323K}$ vs $\log k_{303K}$ ($r=0.996$, $s=0.06$) is 274 (272)* and 276 (273)* in H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ medium (Figs. 2E, F and 2G, H), respectively. This value

* Values obtained in aqueous acetic acid and in aqueous (paranthesis value) media.

is fairly in good agreement with that obtained from the isokinetic relationship.

However, the isokinetic temperature obtained from both the methods are below the experimental temperature (298 to 333 K) and hence this reaction series may be considered to be under the control of $\Delta S^\ddagger$, according to the concept of Bunnett¹⁵. The good correlation obtained in the isokinetic relationship also leads to the conclusion¹⁵ that, the mechanism of the reaction between Br(V) and all the diols are one and the same.

The entropy of activation for all the reactions of diols with acid bromate have been found to be negative. This is due to compactness of the transition state as compared to the ground state, causing a restriction on the translational and rotational freedom, thus reducing the entropy of the system. Further, the large negative entropies of activation are expected for a bimolecular reaction with high polar transition state¹⁶.

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